

Diversifying tree species composition within Scots pine forests – does it increase resilience for biodiversity?

A DiversiTree Research Note March 2025

Research summary

Diversification of tree species within forests is proposed as a mechanism to increase forest resilience both against climate change and pests and pathogens. We explore if increased tree species diversity would provide greater resilience for the biodiversity associated with Scots pine.

1589 species were found to use Scots pine in the UK: 17 birds, 130 bryophytes, 539 fungi, 420 invertebrates, and 15 mammals with 468 lichen species known to use pine, but the species of pine is unknown. Of these 1589 species 199 fungi and 16 invertebrate species are only known to be found on Scots pine together with the 12 lichen species that are only found on pine trees (pine species unknown).

In total 561 species were identified of being at risk if Scots pine were to decline in abundance as they are either only found on Scots pine or rarely use other tree species. One hundred and seventy-one of these species have some form of conservation protection. Of these 22 are obligate on Scots pine, 28 highly associated and four highly associated at the tree genera level. These 54 species may be viewed as the most at risk species if Scots pine were to decline as they are closely associated with Scots pine and their populations are already low or declining.

We assessed 47 other tree species for whether they would support the Scots pine-associated biodiversity. However, **none of the 47 tree species assessed supported the majority of the species found on Scots pine**. Native oak, beech and birch together with shrub species such as alder, hazel, hawthorn, aspen, and rowan were the best tree species to provide support for Scots pine associated biodiversity. The non-native trees Norway spruce and European and Japanese larch also supported some of the Scots pine associated biodiversity.

We conclude that **tree species diversification won't provide resilience for much of the biodiversity associated with Scots pine**. Resilience for Scots pine associated biodiversity therefore needs to be provided through management such as improved biosecurity and reducing fire risk.

Background

Increasing the resilience of our forests is critical due to the increase in tree diseases and climate change. Increasing the species diversity of trees established spreads the risk load, since different trees are likely to have different vulnerabilities to pests and pathogens, drought, frost, wind and wildfire (Atkinson et al., 2022). Increased tree diversity may lead to increased resilience for forest associated species and functioning through functional redundancy, where trees with similar traits can substitute for one another (Ellison et al., 2005, Mitchell et al., 2022). Thus, if one tree declines in abundance the functioning of the system is maintained by other trees.

Scots pine is the UK's only native conifer of economic significance, accounting for 17% of the conifer area in Great Britain (218,000 ha) (Forestry Commission, 2014). It is planted for timber production but is also the dominant species in the culturally iconic native Caledonian pinewoods. While considered native in Scotland Scots pine is considered a non-native or honorary native in the rest of the UK and many Scots pine forests outside of Scotland are managed for biodiversity in addition to timber. Scots pine is at risk from *Dothistroma* needle blight (Brown and Webber, 2008) and a new disease caused by three main agents, *Curreya pithyophila*, *Pineus pini* and *Crumenulopsis sororia* (Green et al., 2024)

The DiversiTree Project

[DiversiTree](#) is part of the [Future of UK Treescapes programme](#). It aimed to provide woodland managers with the knowledge and tools needed to help them to increase the resilience of their woodlands to climate change, and pests and diseases.

We wanted to:

- ❖ Produce a list of the biodiversity supported by Scots pine within the UK.
- ❖ Assess the potential of a range of other tree species to support the biodiversity found on Scots pine
- ❖ Assess whether tree species diversification will increase resilience for Scots pine associated biodiversity.

This research note summarises our research results.

Our research methods are included as Appendix 1.

Scots pine regeneration at Mar Lodge

Results

The biodiversity supported by Scots pine in the UK

One thousand, five hundred and eighty-nine species were found to use Scots pine in the UK, composed of 17 birds, 130 bryophytes, 539 fungi, 420 invertebrates, and 15 mammals with 468 lichen species known to use pine, but the species of pine is unknown (Table 1). The number of fungi associated is an under-estimation as only obligate, high and partial fungi were collated. The 199 obligate fungi species and 16 obligate invertebrate species which are only found on Scots pine together with the 12 lichen species that are only found on pine species would be most at risk if Scots pine were to decline in abundance (Table 1). In addition, there were 230 fungi species and 79 invertebrate species which were classed as highly associated, so rarely found on other tree species, together with 25 lichen species

that rarely use trees other than pine. These highly associated species are also identified as being at risk of population decline if Scots pine were to decline giving a total of 561 species classed as at “risk”.

One hundred and seventy-one of these species have some form of conservation protection. Of these 22 are obligate on Scots pine, 28 highly associated and four highly associated at the tree genera level. These 54 species may be viewed as the most at risk species if Scots pine were to decline as they are closely associated with Scots pine and their populations are already low or declining.

Most species (805) use Scots pine for directly feeding or as a living space (638), a few species are also associated with Scots pine using it indirectly for feeding (199). Dead wood, particularly fallen dead wood and standing dead wood, were shown to be particularly important for many of the species.

Table 1. The number of species in different taxon groups associated with Scots pine

Level of association	Taxon group						Total
	Bird	Bryophyte	Fungi	Invert	Lichen	Mammal	
Obligate			199	16			215
Obligate_genera					12		12
High			230	79			309
High_genera					25		25
Partial	5	2	110	91		1	209
Partial_genera					226		226
Cosmopolitan	9	68		81			158
Cosmopolitan_genera		60		4	205		269
Uses	3			141		14	158
Uses_genera				8			8
Total	17	130	539	420	468	15	1589

*See Table 2 for definitions of levels of association

Broad leaved tree regeneration within a largely Scots pine dominated forest at Mar Lodge

Other tree species that will support the biodiversity found on Scots pine

We assessed if 47 other tree species (Table 3) would support the biodiversity found on Scots pine.

Using the data with the greatest confidence (Yes_species) oak, beech and birch were the best native species to support Scots pine associated biodiversity, supporting 15-16% of the 1363 species Scots pine associated species that are non-obligate and not parasitic (Figure 1). Common alder, hazel, hawthorn, aspen, and rowan all support 5-10% of the non-obligate associated species, while the other native trees support less than 5%. Sycamore and sweet chestnut are naturalized in the UK and support 7% and 5% of the non-obligate associated species. Of the non-native tree species Norway spruce will support 15% of the non-obligate species, European larch, lodgepole pine, Sitka spruce, Douglas fir and European silver fir will all support 5-8%. Maritime pine, Radiata pine, Western Hemlock, Japanese larch, Ponderosa pine, Noble fir, Grand fir, Coast redwood, Western red cedar, Lawson's cypress, Roble, Leyland cypress, Pacific silver fir, Hybrid larch, Giant redwood, Japanese red cedar and Lutz's spruce will support less

than 5% but this is often because information on their suitability is lacking.

The number of different alternative trees that any species would use was typically low: 11% of non-obligate species would only use one other alternative tree species out of the 47 assessed and 23% of non-obligate species would only use one to three other tree species (Figure 2). Only 6% of species would use 10 or more of the other tree species.

Lots of different tree species are required to support even a fraction of the biodiversity found on Scots pine. For example, the "best" combination of five native/naturalized trees to support the greatest number of Scots pine-associated species would in total across the five tree species only support 25% of the non-obligate Scots pine-associated species (Figure 3). If non-native species are included in the mix, then five tree species could support 35% of the species. The increase in the number of additional species supported reduced beyond mixes of five tree species.

Figure 1. The number of Scots pine associated species supported by other tree species. See Table 4 for definitions of levels of association

Figure 2. The number of different alternative tree species used by Scots pine-associated species.

Figure 3. The cumulative number of Scots pine-associated species supported as tree species are added to the mix.

Practical Implications & Recommendations

Our research has shown that tree species diversification won't provide resilience for much of the biodiversity associated with Scots pine because many of the associated species won't use or only rarely use other tree species. Resilience for Scots pine associated biodiversity therefore needs to be provided through management such as improved biosecurity and reducing fire risk.

Native shrubs such as alder, hazel, hawthorn, aspen, and rowan in addition to oak, beech and birch could be included within pine forests to provide support for those species that will use other trees. However, these species are

all broad-leaved trees which will alter the other ecosystem services delivered (e.g. cultural value, recreation, nutrient cycling).

Where planting of non-native tree species is acceptable, non-native pines, Norway spruce and larches will also provide support for this biodiversity, but these trees are also at risk from disease.

Site specific strategies will need to identify which of the alternative tree species are most appropriate at a site level, both in terms of growing conditions, soils and climate, but also for hosting the local biodiversity as not all the biodiversity listed as Scots pine associated-species" in this study will be present at any site.

Appendix 1: Research methods

We did extensive search of published and grey literature and biological records data in 2023/24. The purpose of this investigation was to identify as comprehensively as possible those species that use Scots pine in the UK and the nature of this association.

The data collation was confined to species that use the tree (as a habitat space, or for feeding either directly eating part of the tree or for feeding on other species that use the tree). We did not include species that use the wider forest environment such as open glades or rides. Thus data collation was confined to six taxon groups: birds, bryophytes, invertebrates, fungi, lichens and mammals. The level of association of each species with Scots pine within the UK was recorded as 'obligate', 'high', 'partial', 'cosmopolitan' or 'uses' (Table 2).

Information on the conservation status of associated species was recorded. We grouped these according to whether the species was known to have some form of

conservation protection, as different taxon groups have different measures of conservation categorisation.

Forty-seven tree and shrub species (collectively termed alternative trees (Table 2)) were assessed for their potential to support the Scots pine-associated species. These 47 trees contained species that could be grown for commercial timber (Haufe et al., 2021), and a range of native trees and shrubs that either currently co-occur with Scots pine in Caledonian pine forests (Rodwell, 1991) or are recommended for planting with Scots pine in native woodland mixes (Hotchkiss and Herbert, 2022). The level of use of the 47 alternative trees was categorised according to whether the species was known to use that tree, or just that genus of tree and if the species regularly used the tree or only rarely (Table 4).

Table 2: Criteria used to assess the level of association of biodiversity with Scots pine in the UK. This includes species dependent on other species that use Sitka spruce, such as parasites and some of the predatory insects.

Association with Sitka spruce in UK	Definition
Obligate	Unknown from other tree species/cannot complete its life cycle without using Scots pine.
High	Rarely uses other tree species
Partial	Uses Scots pine more frequently than its availability
Cosmopolitan	Uses Scots pine as frequently or lower than availability
Uses	Uses Scots pine but the importance of Scots pine for this species is unknown
Obligate_genera	Unknown from tree species other than pines/cannot complete its life cycle without using pine but information not available about which pine species is used.
High_genera	Rarely uses tree genera other than pine but information not available about which pine species is/are used.
Partial_genera	Uses pine trees more frequently than their availability but information not available about which pine species is/are used.
Cosmopolitan_genera	Uses pine trees as frequently or lower than their availability but information not available about which pine species is/are used.
Uses_genera	Uses pine trees but the importance of the pine for this species is unknown and information is not available about which pine species is/are used.

Table 3. Tree species assessed for their potential to host the biodiversity supported by Scots pine.

English name ⁵	Latin name	Native
European silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	N
Pacific silver fir	<i>Abies amabilis</i>	N
Grand fir	<i>Abies grandis</i>	N
Noble fir	<i>Abies procera</i>	N
Sycamore	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	N ³
Common alder	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	Y
Birch Silver or Downy	<i>Betula pendula/pubescens</i>	Y ²
Hornbeam	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	Y
Sweet chestnut	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	N ³
Lawson's cypress	<i>Chamaecyparis lawsoniana</i>	N
Hazel	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	Y ¹
Hawthorn	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	Y ¹
Japanese red cedar	<i>Cryptomeria japonica</i>	N
Leyland cypress	<i>Cuprocyparis leylandii</i>	N
Beech	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	Y
Holly	<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	Y ¹
Juniper	<i>Juniperus communis</i>	Y ¹
Hybrid larch	<i>Larix × marschlinii</i>	N ⁴
European Larch	<i>Larix decidua</i>	N ⁴
Japanese larch	<i>Larix kaempferi</i>	N ⁴
Crab apple	<i>Malus sylvestris</i>	Y ¹
Roble	<i>Nothofagus obliqua</i>	N
Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	N ⁴
Sitka Spruce	<i>Picea sitchensis</i>	N ⁴
Lutz's spruce	<i>Picea x lutzii</i>	N
Lodgepole pine	<i>Pinus contorta</i>	N
Maritime pine	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	N
Ponderosa pine	<i>Pinus ponderosa</i>	N
Radiata pine	<i>Pinus radiata</i>	N
Aspen	<i>Populus tremula</i>	Y
Wild cherry	<i>Prunus avium</i>	Y
Bird cherry	<i>Prunus padus</i>	Y ¹
Blackthorn	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	Y ¹
Douglas fir	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	N
Oak (sessile/pedunculate)	<i>Quercus petraea/robur</i>	Y
Goat willow	<i>Salix caprea</i>	Y ¹
Grey willow	<i>Salix cinerea</i>	Y ¹
Coast redwood	<i>Sequoia sempervirens</i>	N
Giant redwood	<i>Sequoiadendron giganteum</i>	N
Rowan	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	Y ²
Wild service-tree	<i>Sorbus torminalis</i>	Y
Yew	<i>Taxus baccata L.</i>	Y
Western red cedar	<i>Thuja plicata Donn</i>	N
Small leaved lime	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	Y
Large leaved lime	<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>	Y
Western Hemlock	<i>Tsuga heterophylla</i>	N
Wych elm	<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	Y

Notes for Table 3

¹Could be included as shrub to increase biodiversity value in native woodland plantings with Scots pine

²Listed as present in the national vegetation classification for native Caledonian Scots pine woods (W18 *Pinus sylvestris-Hylocomium splendens*)

³Non-native but naturalized.

⁴Listed as occasionally present in the W18 *Pinus sylvestris-Hylocomium splendens* woods due to natural colonisation of non-native invasive regeneration

⁵The legislation with respect to which non-native tree species can be planted differs between the four countries within the UK. The inclusion of a species in this table does not imply that it can be legally planted and the relevant legislation should be checked.

Scots pine plantation at Ballogie

Table 4. Definitions of criteria used to assess association of Scots pine-associated species with the 47 alternative tree species listed in Table 2.

Association	Definition
Yes_Sp	Known to use the alternative tree species.
Yes_Gen	Known to use the genera of the alternative tree species but no information on if it will use this species
Rarely_Sp	The associated species has been recorded on this tree species but very rarely, so unlikely to be a good alternative tree species
Rarely_Gen	The associated species has very occasionally been recorded on the genera of the alternative tree species but no information on if it will use this species. Unlikely to be a good alternative tree species
No	Not known to use this tree species
Parasite	Species is a parasite, so no assessment of alternative tree species made
Probable	Based on ecological knowledge of the species the associated species is thought likely or probable to use this tree species but there are no records of the species using this particular tree species. For example, the species is known to use a wide range of deciduous tree species, thus it is probable that it will also occur on other deciduous tree species, even if no records of its occurrence on this tree species exist.
Unknown	The use (or otherwise) of this tree is unknown

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Scots pine plantation at Speymouth with Sitka spruce regenerating in the understory

Links to related research outputs for more detail

Mitchell, R.J.; Albon, S.D.; Bellamy, P.E.; Ellis, C.J.; Hodgetts, N.G.; Johnstone, C.; Stockan, J.A.; Taylor, A.F.S. (2025). Scots pine-associated biodiversity in the UK (Scots pine Ecol). NERC EDS Environmental Information Data Centre. <https://doi.org/10.5285/97f8c19b-7451-4809-b011-0f9cf3eb8430>

Mitchell R.J., Albon S.D., Bellamy P.E., Cameron C, Ellis CJ, Hodgetts N.G., Johnstone C., Stockan J.A., Taylor A.F.S. (in prep) Pining for Diversity: Does greater tree species diversity increase the resilience of *Pinus sylvestris* forests and associated biodiversity in the UK?

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